

Unisoner: An Interactive Interface for Derivative Chorus Creation from Various Singing Voices on the Web

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes *Unisoner*, an interface for assisting the creation of derivative choruses in which voices of different singers singing the same song are overlapped on one common accompaniment. It was time-consuming to create such derivative choruses because creators have to manually cut and paste fragments of singing voices from different singers, and then adjust the timing and volume of every fragment. Although several interfaces for mashing up different songs have been proposed, no mash-up interface for creating derivative choruses by mixing singing voices for the same song has been reported. *Unisoner* enables users to find appropriate singers by using acoustic features and metadata of the singing voices to be mixed, assign icons of the found singers to each phrase within a song, and adjust the mixing volume by moving those icons. *Unisoner* thus enables users to easily and intuitively create derivative choruses. It is implemented by using several signal processing techniques, including a novel technique that integrates F_0 -estimation results from many voices singing the same song to reliably estimate F_0 without octave errors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Derivative singings, cover versions of existing original songs, are common in the age of digital music production and sharing [1]. Many amateur singers sing a same song and upload their singing voices to video sharing services. Those derivative singings are called “Me Singing”, and 1.7 million “Me Singing” videos have been uploaded on a popular video sharing service *YouTube*¹, and 665,000 videos have been uploaded on a Japanese video sharing service, *Niconico*². These derivative singings make it possible for people to listen to and compare voices of different singers singing the same song. Since derivative singings are so popular, many (amateur) artists have provided karaoke versions to make it easier to create derivative singings.

Some creators have started creating derivative works of such derivative singings by mixing (mashing up) them

Figure 1. Relationship among original songs, derivative singings, derivative choruses, and listeners. Various singers sing the same song to create derivative singings. From these singings, derivative choruses are created. Many listeners enjoy not only the original songs, but also the derivative singings and choruses.

along with one common accompaniment. We call this type of music *derivative chorus*. Figure 1 shows the relationship among original songs, derivative singings, and derivative choruses. Approximately 10,000 derivative choruses have been uploaded on Niconico, and some derivative choruses have received more than 1 million views³.

Derivative choruses are similar to Eric Whitacre’s “Virtual Choir”⁴. Virtual Choir was created by mixing singing voices that were purposely recorded and uploaded for this collaborative choir. In contrast, though, derivative choruses simply reuse existing derivative singings that are not intended to be mixed with other singings.

Listeners can enjoy derivative choruses in the following ways:

Listen to different expressions of derivative choruses

Famous original songs tend to have several derivative choruses. Even if the original song is the same, the derivative singings used and their arrangement (the way of mashing up them) are different in each derivative chorus. Listeners can enjoy comparing such different singings and arrangements.

Compare characteristics of singers

Listening to several

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¹ <http://www.youtube.com>

² <http://www.nicovideo.jp>

³ A derivative chorus at <http://www.nicovideo.jp/watch/sm5132988> has more than 1.9 million views.

⁴ <http://ericwhitacre.com/the-virtual-choir>

Figure 2. Overview of Unisoner and the interaction between user and Unisoner.

derivative singings at the same time allows listeners to notice differences in singing style, vocal timbre, etc.

Discover favorite singers Derivative choruses give listeners a chance to discover singers they like from the derivative singings used in the choruses. Some creators of derivative choruses mash up derivative singings to highlight their favorite singers.

Creators of derivative choruses can also enjoy the derivative creation.

It was, however, not easy to create derivative choruses. First, it is necessary to extract singing voices from derivative singings by suppressing their karaoke accompaniments. Second, since the extracted singing voices are not temporally aligned, it is time-consuming to synchronize them with a karaoke accompaniment. Third, creators must use a waveform-editing tool, such as Digital Audio Workstation (DAW), to manually cut and paste fragments of singing voices from different singers.

We therefore propose an easy-to-use interface, *Unisoner*, that enables end users without musical expertise to create derivative choruses. Unisoner overcomes the difficulties described above by automating the synchronization tasks necessary for derivative choruses and providing intuitive mixing functions. This work forms part of the emerging field of creative Music Information Retrieval (MIR), where MIR techniques are used for creative purposes. In this field, there have been interfaces for creating mash-up music by connecting loops corresponding to musical pieces [2], creating mash-up music automatically [3], and creating mash-up dance videos [4], yet no interface for derivative choruses has been reported.

In addition to Unisoner, we also propose a singing training interface that leverages various derivative singings. Since amateur singers have difficulty improving their singing skill, singing training interfaces, such as an interface to analyze a singer's voice alone [5] and an interface to compare two singing voices [6], have been proposed.

Our training interface allows a user to compare his or her singing with a wide variety of derivative singings by visualizing them. The user can choose a favorite existing singing by using metadata such as the number of views on a video sharing service, and compare the fundamental frequency (F_0) of the chosen singing with the F_0 of the user's singing so that the user can sing more like the favorite singing.

Demonstration videos of Unisoner are available at <http://mmlab.cs.tsukuba.ac.jp/%7etsuzuki/icmcsmc14>.

2. UNISONER: INTERACTIVE DERIVATIVE CHORUS CREATION INTERFACE

Unisoner enables users to create derivative choruses easily, and allows for the simultaneous listening of various derivative singings and derivative choruses. We assume audio signals have been extracted from a set of desired videos on YouTube or NicoNico. We call the resulting audio signal the *accompanied singing*, and the vocal audio signal after vocal extraction (see Section 3) the *suppressed singing*.

2.1 Interface of Unisoner

Figure 2 shows an overview of Unisoner. Creators of derivative choruses using conventional methods (e.g., waveform-editing tools) had to work hard to make derivative choruses, such as by cutting and pasting fragments of suppressed singings or adjusting the volume of each suppressed singing. Unisoner provides users with an easy-to-use interface to overcome these difficulties.

Unisoner displays each suppressed singing as an icon that represents each singer (the singer icon). A user can assign each singing to phrases and adjust volume simply by dragging and dropping singer icons. Moreover, music-synchronized lyrics, given in advance, enable the user to assign each singing to certain phrases easily.

Figure 3. Comparison of waveform-editing tools and Unisoner.

The smooth assignment of each singing to phrases is important for efficient creation of derivative choruses. Unisoner dynamically synthesizes the chorus according to the user's operations. Thus, a user can check the output chorus instantly without stopping the music. The creation of derivative choruses in real-time with Unisoner can be regarded as an example of active music listening [7]. Unisoner and standard tools are compared in Figure 3.

2.2 Three functions of Unisoner

Unisoner features the following three main functions.

1) Lyrics-based phrase selection Users must be able to intuitively select desired phrases to efficiently create derivative choruses. Phrase selection on conventional waveform-editing tools is inefficient because it is difficult to select correct phrases just by looking at waveforms. It is, however, time-consuming for users to listen to each fragment of singing. Unisoner can select and jump to the phrase of interest by leveraging the song lyrics (marked **A** in Figure 2).

Users can divide a song into sections that include multiple phrases and assign singings to sections. Operations related to song lyrics and sections are illustrated in left figure of Figure 2. In those operations, the copy-and-paste function along with drag-and-drop is a unique feature of Unisoner. Though waveform-editing tools can copy waveforms, they cannot copy *only* information on the assigned singing and the volume of each singing. This is clearly useful when a user wants to use the same singing at the same volume on a different section, such as when equalizing the assigned singing on the first and second verse.

As a way to use clickable lyrics, skipping the playback position [8] and selecting the position for recording [9] has been proposed. However, selecting sections and enabling the user to edit derivative choruses based on lyrics is a novel idea regarding the usage of clickable lyrics.

2) Real-time assignment and volume control of singings using icons Waveform-editing tools enable music creators to adjust the volume of the left and right channels of each suppressed singing in detail, but this becomes increasingly cumbersome as the number of vocal tracks increases. Unisoner represents each suppressed singing as an icon (**B**

in Figure 2), colored according to the estimated gender-likeness of the singer (as explained in Section 3.5), so the user can intuitively understand how each suppressed singing is sung and how high the volume of each suppressed singing is. The overall volume of each suppressed singing can be adjusted by moving the singer icon to the front or back, and the volume balance between two channels can be adjusted by moving the singer icon left or right on the stage (**C** in Figure 2). The balance between the left and right channels is decided automatically so that the total energy is evenly divided between the two channels.

These forms of volume control and the assignment of singing to phrase using icons can be done in real-time without stopping the music. The real-time assignment of singings assists a user's trial-and-error approach to creation. While waveform-editing tools do not allow editing and listening at the same time, Unisoner lets the user seamlessly edit and listen to the output chorus, thus allowing users to concentrate on the selection of singing to be assigned.

3) Sorting and filtering using metadata and acoustic features

The sorting and filtering of derivative singings allow a user to explore thousands of derivative singings. Unisoner can sort and filter derivative singings by acoustic features and metadata. Sorting criteria obtained from acoustic features are the similarity of singing style and voice timbre to focused singing. Criteria obtained from metadata are the singer's name⁵, the number of views, and the number of Mylists ("favorites" put by users). Filtering criteria are the gender-likeness of singing and the key difference from the original song, which are both obtained from acoustic features. Acoustic features used in sorting and filtering are explained in Section 3. These various forms of sorting and filtering can be done by clicking a button on Unisoner (**D** in Figure 2). This is a feature not provided by waveform-editing tools.

2.3 Typical use of Unisoner

By clicking the lyric (**E** in Figure 2), a user can change the current playback position to focus on a certain section. A suppressed singing will be added to the specified section of choice by dragging-and-dropping the corresponding singer icon (**F** in Figure 2). The volume of each singing can be adjusted by moving the singer icon. For creation of derivative choruses with specific features, such as a derivative chorus with only male singers, the filtering and sorting functions are essential. The Auto button (**G** in Figure 2) can be employed when the user lacks a creative spark. Unisoner automatically divides the song into sections and randomly assigns singings into each section when the Auto button is clicked.

2.4 Application of a derivative chorus into singing training

Unisoner can also be used for singing training; since most of the singings are sung in the same musical structure,

⁵ Uploaders' names are currently used for substitute of singer's name.

Figure 4. Screenshot of the proposed singing training interface.

singers can learn how to sing a song from an existing derivative singing. A proposed singing training interface (Figure 4) utilizes various derivative singings of the same song as a reference to help users recognize their singing characteristics, which is important for improving singing skill. To achieve this, visualization of the F_0 of singing voices is effective. Conventional singing training interfaces [5, 6] also visualize the F_0 of a singing voice for training. Our proposed interface visualizes F_0 of the user's singing, F_0 of various derivative singings, and the overlapped F_0 of thousands of singings at the same time.

Because many derivative singings have been uploaded on the Web, recommendation of an appropriate derivative singing is necessary to find a good set of references. Our proposed singing training interface recommends based on the similarity of singing style and vocal timbre, and shows the number of views and the number of Mylists for the referred singing. With recommendations regarding both timbre and style, users can use metadata to predict how their recording will be ranked when uploaded. With the voice timbre recommendation, users can know what kinds of sound are currently popular. Recommendation regarding voice timbre also enables users to compare singing styles to improve their singing skills. By comparing his or her singing to similar singing, the user can more easily imagine how it will sound when they sing in a different way. This will help users widen the expression range of their singing.

2.4.1 Operation of proposed singing training interface

The singing training interface can be used by the following steps. This interface helps users recognize their particular singing specialty by comparing various derivative singings which are similar.

Selection of basis singing A user selects the singing that will be used as a search reference. The user can click buttons on the left side of the display (A in Figure 4) or can drag and drop a file with data on their singing. The number of views and Mylists are displayed on buttons. F_0 of the selected singing (the "basis singing") is indicated by the red line in the center (B in Figure 4). In addition, overlapped F_0 lines of all singing examples are shown in black

Figure 5. Comparison of F_0 of basis singing, that of reference singing, and overall F_0 of all singers. F_0 of basis singing differs from that of both reference singing and the majority of all singers.

lines. The more singings sung with that F_0 in that time frame, the darker the overall contour becomes.

Selection of reference singing Candidate singings which are close to the selected singing with respect to certain criteria are displayed on the right-side buttons (C in Figure 4). Users can select a reference by clicking these buttons, after which the F_0 of the reference is indicated by the blue line (B in Figure 4). When the play button (D in Figure 4) is clicked, the basis singing is played from the left channel, with the reference singing played from the right channel.

Selection of criteria for recommendation The criteria for recommendation can be changed by clicking the upper right buttons (E in Figure 4). Users can select the recommendation criteria from the similarity of voice timbre, calculated from the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficient (MFCC), the similarity of singing style, calculated from F_0 and ΔF_0 , and the overall similarity, which includes all of these (methods to calculate these similarities are described in Section 3.4). Moreover, users can filter the recommendation results by the number of views, enabling comparison between a user's singing and references which are both close to the user's singing and popular.

2.4.2 Recognizing the specialty of a user's singing voice using the proposed interface

By visualizing a particular F_0 contour, a user can easily see the differences between singings and can get an idea of how to sing by listening. In a situation such as that of Figure 5, the red line (the user's singing) and blue line (reference) are clearly different. Comparing these two lines and the black lines in the background, it is apparent that the blue line is closer to the area where the black lines are concentrated (the dark black area). Since black lines indicate the trend in F_0 , it can be said that this user's singing differs from that of the majority of singers. This enables understanding of deviations from the norm in this singing example. After this analysis, the user can listen to the reference and practice singing to adjust the pitch.

Figure 6. The preprocessing flow. Derivative singings are collected from the Web and resampled into 16 kHz signals. The key difference and time delay from the original singing are then estimated. Last, accompaniments included in the derivative singings are suppressed.

3. IMPLEMENTATION OF UNISONER

We implemented Unisoner by developing a new F_0 estimation method that utilizes various derivative singings of the same song. Unisoner is also based on various methods, such as karaoke accompaniment suppression, similarity calculation between suppressed singings, and gender-likeness estimation of suppressed singings.

In Unisoner, all accompanied and suppressed singings are sampled at 16 kHz, and they are monaural. We assume that the karaoke accompaniments used in derivative singing are given, because these are open to the public in many cases⁶.

3.1 Songs and data used in Unisoner

We chose an original song that has the largest number of derivative singings in Niconico⁷. We collected videos of those derivative singings as well as the karaoke version of the original song. 4,941 derivative singing videos were collected from Niconico in total, and the numbers of views and Mylists attached to each video were also collected. However, the collected singing videos included some videos which were inappropriate for analysis, such as remixed songs of the original song. We filtered out singing videos that were more than 15 seconds shorter or longer than the original song to avoid this problem. As a result, 4488 derivative singing videos were used for Unisoner and the signal processing described below.

3.2 Preprocessing

The estimation of key and time differences from the original song and the suppression of karaoke accompaniments make up the preprocessing steps in Unisoner. These steps are illustrated in Figure 6. For computational efficiency,

⁶Hamasaki *et al.* reported that many VOCALOID song writers publish karaoke versions of their songs [1], for example.

⁷A song at <http://www.nicovideo.jp/watch/sm15630734> are chosen.

the key difference is first estimated with broad time resolution, after which the time delay is estimated at a finer resolution. The first estimation is done with a hop time of 100 ms, and the second estimation is done with a hop time of $62.5\mu\text{s}$ or 1 sample.

Key difference and rough time delay estimation The key difference from the original singing is estimated by calculating the two-dimensional cross correlation of a log-frequency spectrogram of accompanied singing and karaoke accompaniments. This calculation has to be done in *two dimensions* because the differences of both key and time have to be calculated simultaneously. Log-frequency spectrograms, calculated by getting the inner product with a windowed frame, are used because the differences in keys will be described as linear differences by using log-frequency. We use a Hanning window of 2,048 samples and a hop size of 1,600 samples. The log-frequency spectrogram is calculated in the range of 1 to 128 in MIDI note number (8.7 to 13289.7 Hz) and 1 bin is allocated for each note number. The MIDI note number f_M can be calculated by the following equation when f_{Hz} is the frequency in Hz:

$$f_M = 12 \log_2 \left(\frac{f_{\text{Hz}}}{440} \right) + 69. \quad (1)$$

The estimation result is limited to between ± 6 MIDI notes of the original song. Note that many singers sing the exact same melody as the original, and that our method is invariant to octave choice by the singer. Compared to the hand-labeled key difference, 96 out of 100 singing samples were estimated correctly. There were 50 singing samples with a key difference and the other samples were in the same key as the original song. Pitch-shifted karaoke accompaniments are used for the following preprocessing on accompanied singing with a different key. Audacity⁸ is used to make pitch-shifted sound.

Estimation of precise time delay The time delay between accompanied singing $g_1(t)$ and karaoke accompaniment $g_2(t)$ is estimated in samples using the cross correlation function $\phi(\tau)$

$$\phi(\tau) = \sum_t g_1(t)g_2(t-\tau), \quad (2)$$

where t and τ represent samples. By shifting each accompanied singing by τ^* samples, which maximizes $\phi(\tau)$ as follows

$$\tau^* = \underset{\tau}{\operatorname{argmax}} \phi(\tau), \quad (3)$$

the start time of all accompanied singings can be snapped to match the karaoke accompaniments. τ^* is limited to a range of ± 0.05 seconds of the roughly estimated delay calculated in the previous step.

The median difference between hand-labeled samples and the estimated time delay in the 100 singing samples, where the same samples are used as for the evaluation of key difference, was 0.0346 seconds.

⁸<http://audacity.sourceforge.net>

Suppression of karaoke accompaniments Karaoke accompaniments in accompanied singing are suppressed by spectral subtraction [10]:

$$S(\omega) = \begin{cases} 0 & (H(\omega) \leq 0) \\ H(\omega)e^{j \arg X(\omega)} & (\text{otherwise}), \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$H(\omega) = |X(\omega)| - \alpha|W(\omega)|, \quad (5)$$

where $X(\omega)$ and $W(\omega)$ are spectrals of the accompanied singing and karaoke accompaniments. α is a parameter, describing the weight for subtracting the karaoke, and j is the imaginary unit.

The quality of suppressed singing is sensitive to the choice of α . Thus, an appropriate α for each accompanied singing must be estimated before suppression. To determine α , the karaoke accompaniment is temporarily suppressed with $\alpha = 1$, and non-vocal sections are estimated from the result of suppression. These sections are classified as an area where power is lower than the pre-defined threshold (average power of the full mix). Power is calculated with a Hanning window of 1,024 samples, FFT with 2,048 samples, and a hop size of 512 samples.

After estimation of non-vocal sections, karaoke accompaniment is suppressed on the longest non-vocal section for each α , which increases by 0.1 from 0 to 5. Minimum α , where the power of singing after suppression is lower than the threshold, are treated as an appropriate α for accompaniment suppression of the whole song. 1% of the power of singing before suppression is currently used as a threshold. Note that $|S(\omega)|$ tends to be smaller in the non-vocal section than in the vocal section, no matter what α is, because accompanied singing and karaoke accompaniments have almost the same signal in a non-vocal section. To determine α and suppress karaoke accompaniment, a Hanning window of 2048 samples, FFT calculated with 4096 samples, and a hop size of 1024 samples are used.

3.3 F_0 estimation method integrating various derivative singings

An effective F_0 estimation method for suppressed singing is needed to enable sorting according to a singers' singing style. We used the SWIPE algorithm [11] as a base method for F_0 estimation. It is calculated with a time resolution of 10 ms and frequency resolution of 0.1 MIDI notes.

Though SWIPE is a highly precise method, estimation errors sometimes occur (such as in the upper plot of Figure 7) when it is applied to suppressed singing. In this research, we propose an F_0 estimation method that leverages various derivative singings. We assume that even if each estimation result includes some errors, the trends appearing in results will be close to the true F_0 value. If this is true, the precision of the F_0 estimation should be improved by searching for the most feasible value around the trend. This method for estimating the range of estimation is an important method for improving estimation efficiency, and can also be applied to other F_0 estimation methods.

Range estimation of F_0 In Figure 8, \textcircled{A} shows the distribution of F_0 values for each suppressed singing. The majority of estimation results are concentrated within a nar-

Figure 7. Upper: F_0 of suppressed singing from estimation in SWIPE (red line). Lower: Estimated F_0 of suppressed singing using the proposed method (blue line). Black lines in both figures show the range of results determined from the trend of F_0 illustrated in Figure 8 and used in the proposed method. Variance in the estimated result was reduced by properly determining the estimation range.

row range of values (indicated by the white lines). Two peaks are shown in the figure, and these peaks can be considered as the F_0 of singings sung like the original song (\pm octave errors). This result suggests that reliable F_0 estimation can be done for each singing by integrating various F_0 estimation results.

In Figure 8, \textcircled{B} shows a histogram of the first 0.1 seconds of \textcircled{A} . Peaks at MIDI note numbers 50 and 62, which have a 1 octave difference, can be observed. Assuming that the true F_0 value of each suppressed singing is near the trend (peak), we regard the most frequently appearing F_0 , considering the 1 octave difference, as the *mode* F_0 of that frame. The mode F_0 can be calculated by adding the number of occurrences of an F_0 value and the occurrence of F_0 values that are 1 octave (12 note number) lower than that F_0 from the lowest to the highest (sum of \textcircled{B} and \textcircled{C} in Figure 8), and then selecting the F_0 value that has the maximum sum (62 in \textcircled{D} of Figure 8).

Re-estimation of F_0 F_0 for each frame is re-estimated by limiting the estimation range around mode F_0 after calculating mode F_0 in every frame. However, it is possible that derivative singings may be sung 1 octave higher or lower than the original (for example, when a male singer sings a song originally recorded by a female singer). To counteract this, the distance between the F_0 value of the first estimation and mode F_0 , mode $F_0 + 1$ octave, and mode $F_0 - 1$ octave are calculated. This distance, D , between the estimated F_0 and mode F_0 is then calculated by

$$D = \sum_t \sqrt{(f_0(t) - f_{\text{mode}}(t))^2}, \quad (6)$$

where t is an index for the time frame, $f_0(t)$ indicates the estimated F_0 , and $f_{\text{mode}}(t)$ indicates mode F_0 .

In re-estimation, ± 3 semitones from the selected candidates was used as the estimation range. Properties such as time and frequency resolution were same with those for the initial estimation. The lower plot in Figure 7 shows the re-estimated F_0 , with the black lines showing the estimation range. Comparing the estimations, we can see that the

Figure 8. A: Distribution of F_0 values 0 to 5 seconds after prelude. The estimation results from 4488 singings were used for this figure. A sharp peak surrounded by a white line can be seen in each time frame. B: Histogram of the appearance of the F_0 value in the first 0.1 seconds of Figure A. Two peaks separated by the distance of a 12 note number can be seen. C: Histogram of Figure B shifted by 12 notes (1 octave). D: Sum of Figures B and C. Mode F_0 is an F_0 value with maximum sum.

variance of the estimated result has decreased from that of the initial estimation.

3.4 Similarity calculation method between singings

To sort acoustic features (Section 2.2), we calculate the similarity between the suppressed singings by using the Earth Movers Distance (EMD) [12] between their Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs).

Voice timbre similarity MFCCs were used as a feature.

The frame length was 25 ms and the hop time was 10 ms for the calculation. The lower 12 dimensions, excluding the DC components, were used.

Singing style similarity F_0 and ΔF_0 were used.

Overall similarity MFCC, F_0 , and ΔF_0 were used.

3.5 Gender-likeness estimation method for derivative singing

Each singer's gender-likeness is estimated from the estimated probability of a two-class (male- and female-class) Support Vector Machine (SVM) [13]. Unisoner sets the color of the singer icon according to the estimated probability of each class. 12-dimensional MFCCs are calculated using a 25-ms frame length and a 10-ms hop time. MFCCs and ΔF_0 from 30 singings of another song (15 male, 15 female) are used for training. The male- and female-likeness are calculated by taking the median of the estimated probability over all frames in each class. The duration between the beginning of the first verse and the end of the first chorus is regarded as a vocal section and used for both training and estimation.

This method is based on the technique used in Songrium [1]. Songrium uses ΔF_0 and LPMCC (mel-cepstral coefficients of LPC spectrum) from *reliable frames* [14] as a feature for SVM. Unisoner, however, uses MFCC as a feature, since MFCC is a common feature for gender estimation [15] and its usefulness in gender recognition tasks of speech has been verified [16].

3.6 Chorus synthesis

Unisoner dynamically synthesizes a derivative chorus according to the assignments of singings to sections. The location of a singer icon in the interface determines the volume.

Determination of overall volume Overall volume is first calculated. The bottom-right area of the Unisoner display resembles a stage with two-step stairs and a user can place each singer icon on the stage (Figure 9) to assign each corresponding singing to a section and adjust the volume of the singing. The overall volume of suppressed singings located on the rear step is multiplied by 0.5, so the volume of singings located on the rear step becomes lower than that of singings on the front step. Let the waveforms of suppressed singing S be $s(t)$. The adjusted waveforms $s'(t)$ are then calculated as

$$s'(t) = \begin{cases} s(t) & (S \text{ locates on front step}) \\ \frac{1}{2}s(t) & (S \text{ locates on rear step}). \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Determination of angle for panning The angle for panning each suppressed singing is then determined. When N singer icons are located on the same floor and a singer icon of suppressed singing S is the m -th singer icon from the right (from the user's view), the localization angle θ of S is determined by

$$\theta = \begin{cases} \frac{m}{N+1}\pi & (N \neq 1 \text{ and } S \text{ is on 1st floor}) \\ \frac{m-1}{N-1}\pi & (N \neq 1 \text{ and } S \text{ is on 2nd floor}) \\ \pi/2 & (N = 1), \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where θ takes the range $[0, \pi]$, as shown in Figure 9. This equation was designed to locate singings on the front step near the center, and to make the number of singings equal on the left and right sides.

Determination of final volume Last, the waveforms of left and right channels, $s'_L(t)$ and $s'_R(t)$, are determined from $s'(t)$ and θ as follows:

$$s'_L(t) = \frac{\theta}{\pi}s'(t), \quad s'_R(t) = (1 - \frac{\theta}{\pi})s'(t). \quad (9)$$

3.7 Other data needed for implementation

A map between the lyrics and the waveform of suppressed singing, used for lyrics-based phrase selection (section 2.2), and timing for dividing the song, used for automatic synthesis of the chorus (section 2.3), are needed to implement Unisoner. These data are currently prepared by the user, although the application of existing techniques such as lyric alignment [8] or chorus detection [17] could make these user tasks unnecessary in the future.

Figure 9. Upper: Parameters to decide volume. Lower: Amplitude variation of each singing in left speaker ($s'_L(t)$) and right speaker ($s'_R(t)$) corresponding to θ .

4. DISCUSSION

Unisoner was designed for users unfamiliar with the creation of music or software for creating music (such as waveform-editing tools). Because each derivative singing is itself a complete music piece, derivative choruses are guaranteed to be lower-bounded in quality. Thus, derivative choruses are well suited for users who are learning to create music using our interface. Unisoner can also be considered an Augmented Music-Understanding Interface [18], since one function of derivative choruses is to support the analysis of singer characteristics.

Derivative singings can be regarded as a kind of open database of cover songs. There are several databases for cover songs, such as the SecondHandSongs dataset⁹, which are linked to the Million Song Dataset [19]. An advantage of derivative singings compared to the usual cover songs is that most derivative singings of a song are sung in the same tempo and the same musical structure as the original song. Thus, they are useful for examining how people listen to songs or what makes songs more appealing. Signal processing techniques for derivative singings, such as those introduced in this paper, may have a potential as a basis of such examination.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we proposed Unisoner, which enables a user to easily and intuitively create derivative choruses by simply dragging-and-dropping icons. Another key feature of Unisoner is phrase selection using lyrics. Unisoner should improve the efficiency of creating derivative choruses compared with using conventional waveform-editing tools. To realize Unisoner, several signal processing methods have been implemented. Among these methods is a new F_0 estimation method that improves precision by considering the trend of each singing's F_0 . Even though each F_0 contains some errors, our method is able to overcome those errors.

In our future work, we will continue to improve the precision of each signal processing method and interface for utilizing derivative singings. For example, we will consider the use of features other than ΔF_0 or MFCCs for estimating the similarity between derivative singings.

⁹ <http://labrosa.ee.columbia.edu/millionsong/secondhand>

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